

D5.2

Documentation and guidelines how to onboard IPTP, IPSP, journals, content, tools to Diamond Discovery Hub

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Abstract	<p>This document presents an overview of the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) documentation, outlining the procedures for onboarding institutional publishers and journals. The documentation covers the platform's mission, its target audiences, as well as the requirements for journal inclusion, including the diamond open access criteria and relevant metadata. It clarifies the roles and responsibilities within the DDH user management system and explains the procedures for becoming a trusted data source. Furthermore, the documentation offers instructions for different user groups, e.g. describing aspects of the journal verification and management for trusted data sources. The documentation deals with data submission, data reuse options, support channels, and covers privacy and accessibility guidelines. Implemented on WordPress as a subpage of the DDH, the documentation is designed as a practical tool for users engaging with the DDH.</p>

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
ICM	Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
OA	Open Access

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document describes the structure and scope of the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) documentation, emphasising the onboarding procedures for institutional publishers and journals. The documentation provides an overview of the DDH platform's purpose, its target audience, the criteria for inclusion of journals as well as the journal metadata in DDH. The documentation details the six diamond open access criteria, requirements for becoming a trusted source, and user roles within the DDH system. Guidance is provided for each user group, covering access to resources, verification procedures, and journal management workflows. Additionally, the documentation addresses practical aspects such as data ingestion, reuse, technical support contacts, as well as privacy and accessibility policies. The comprehensive documentation is maintained on WordPress as part of the DDH's website and supports users in effectively engaging with and contributing to the DDH platform.

2 THE DDH DOCUMENTATION

This deliverable outlines the documentation for the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH), focusing on the onboarding procedures for institutional publishers and journals. The full documentation is implemented on WordPress and is integrated into the DDH system (<https://ddh.diamas.org/docs/>).

Figure 1: Screenshot of the list of diamond journals on the DDH

The DDH documentation contains an overview of the DDH itself, outlining its purpose, scope and intended audience. Central to the platform's content verification are the six diamond open access criteria¹, developed in the Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) and CRAFT-OA projects and validated through various community consultations. The documentation lists them and specifies the conditions for inclusion into the DDH based on these criteria. Beyond the criteria, the DDH system also stores other journal metadata, including allowed values for each metadata field (e.g. International Organization for Standardization (ISO) codes for countries). To support discovery, the documentation explains the DDH's search function, filters and sorting, helping users to navigate the curated list of diamond journals.

An important feature is the DDH's user management system, which distinguishes between General Internet Users, DDH Editors, Trusted Data Source Representatives, and DDH Administrators. The concept of "trusted sources", meaning trustworthy data sources is also explained. These are institutions or services that have formally agreed to the DDH's Terms of

¹ Armengou, C., Bargheer, M., Gingold, A., Holsinger, S., Laakso, M., Mitchell, D., Mounier, P., Pölonen, J., Rooryck, J., Ševkušić, M., Souyiultzoglou, I., & Varachkina, H. (2024). Operational Diamond OA Criteria for Journals. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12721408>

Service, meaning they adopt and apply the diamond criteria, enrich their metadata accordingly, and share their journal data with DDH. Trust implies a reliance on the accuracy and integrity of the data provided, making these sources the main providers of the DDH's content and credibility.

Another significant audience for the DDH documentation are existing and future DDH Editors, a group of representatives from the European institutional publishing community. They curated the initial datasets of journals in the DDH and verified all of them manually. Now as experts for the six Diamond Open Access (OA) criteria, they will further evaluate the data submitted by non-trusted sources.

Furthermore, the documentation provides guidance on how to become a trusted source for the DDH. Publishers, service providers, and technology providers can apply by registering with the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) registry. Upon approval by the EDCH team, they can create an organisation profile in the registry and, as part of this process, express their interest in becoming a trusted source for DDH. After that, DDH representatives initiate contact to ensure that the terms of service for trusted sources are confirmed and to discuss the next steps, including the details of the journal verification task and data ingestion methods. All communication with potential trusted sources will be handled by the administration team and supported by adequate technology, such as a Kanban board. Once the process is agreed upon, the DDH administrator creates user accounts for the data source and its representatives within the DDH system, and the source is ready to submit their verified diamond journals to DDH.

The DDH documentation provides tailored information for each user group. Trusted sources receive a comprehensive set of resources needed to integrate their journals into the DDH, including the above-mentioned terms of service, diamond criteria, verification guidelines, Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) to deal with the verification of difficult and ambiguous cases, available data ingestion methods, as well as detailed explanations of journal management within the DDH (data ownership, updates, deletions, and notifications).

DDH Editors are supported with documentation that outlines their role and responsibilities. Journals benefit from access to diamond self-declaration templates, which facilitates the process of assessing and declaring a journal's compliance with diamond criteria for their institutional publishers. For DDH administrators, the documentation describes the tasks for new administrators, contributing to the sustainability of the service.

Another important aspect of the DDH described in the documentation is the ability to harvest and reuse data. Relevant technical endpoints are included to facilitate this process.

Finally, the documentation provides contact details for both technical and editorial support. It also includes important information on accessibility, privacy and cookies. As one of the

services under the EDCH umbrella², the DDH makes references to it aligning with the broader ecosystem.

As the DDH evolves, the documentation will be adjusted and extended. The University of Göttingen will ensure the maintenance of the documentation with the assistance of Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) Warsaw in the long run.

² <https://diamas.org/services>

3 REFERENCES

3.1 List of References

Armengou, C., Bargheer, M., Gingold, A., Holsinger, S., Laakso, M., Mitchell, D., Mounier, P., Pölönen, J., Rooryck, J., Ševkušić, M., Souyioultzoglou, I., & Varachkina, H. (2024). Operational Diamond OA Criteria for Journals. Zenodo.

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3.2 List of Websites

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